

Modeling surge dynamics improves coastal flood estimates in a global set of tropical cyclones

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Abstract

Tropical cyclone-induced storm surge is a major coastal risk which will be further amplified by rising sea levels under global warming. The surge-induced floodplains are commonly modeled using a two-step approach by first producing coastal water levels which are, secondly, translated into inundated areas. Here, we evaluate an alternative approach where ocean dynamics and coastal inundation are modeled in a single step using the open-source solver GeoClaw that accounts for the event-specific variation over time of flood drivers. We compute the surge-induced flood extents for a global set of 71 storms from 2000-2019. We show that GeoClaw better reproduces satellite observations and high water marks than two different common modeling approaches that lack a process-based representation of inundation dynamics: a state-of-the-art two-step approach combining a full-scale ocean dynamics with a static (bathtub-type) inundation model and a lightweight approach that directly translates parametric tropical cyclone wind fields into inundation maps using statistical relationships. GeoClaw does not reach the performance of the ocean dynamics model in reproducing coastal water levels, but this deficiency is overcompensated by the dynamic modeling of inundated areas. The computational efficiency of the one-step approach opens up new perspectives for global assessments of coastal risks from tropical cyclones.

24 Introduction

25 Tropical cyclones (TCs) are one of the most devastating categories of extreme weather events
26 on earth with their impact concentrated in coastal areas. TCs are connected to only 16%
27 of the weather-related records in the international disasters database EM-DAT, but are still
28 responsible for 41% of the damages (1991-2020)¹. They are so destructive because they
29 encompass multiple hazards: high intensity winds, rain, storm surges, and associated com-
30 pound floods. The cascading effects can exacerbate the damage². An example is Hurricane
31 Harvey that made landfall in Texas in August 2017 with wind gusts of more than 200 kmh
32 (124 mph), a storm surge of more than 2 meters and record rainfall of more than 1100 mm
33 (43 in) within four days. The storm caused 88 deaths and US\$ 94 billion (2015 USD) in direct
34 economic damages¹. Several studies concluded that a large part of Harvey’s destructiveness
35 is due to compound effects from fluvial, pluvial, and surge-induced flooding^{3,4}.

36 To capture the overall impact of TCs well, each of the TC-related hazards wind, rain,
37 inland and coastal flooding needs to be taken into account by modeling frameworks. The
38 largest TC-induced economic damages are overall found to be from freshwater flooding, but
39 the impact of storm surge is still large considering the small area at risk of this hazard⁵⁻⁷. In
40 the USA, storm surge has been found to be the primary cause of fatalities resulting from TCs
41 over the 1963-2012 period⁸, though statistics for the 2013-2022 decade indicate that efforts
42 to improve warnings and education about the risks of TCs might have helped to reduce
43 storm surge-related fatalities⁹. The costliest natural disaster in the USA on record was
44 Hurricane Katrina (2005), where freshwater flooding played a minor role^{10,11}. An analysis of
45 US flood insurance claims from 2001 to 2014 found that 64% of the number of paid claims
46 were freshwater claims, but surge claims account for 49% of the damage⁷. Local and regional
47 impact modeling has confirmed the importance of multiple drivers¹²⁻¹⁵. However, so far most
48 global empirical estimates of TC-induced economic damages use wind¹⁶⁻¹⁹ or pressure²⁰ as
49 the only hazard predictors. One study includes rainfall as an additional driver²¹, but none
50 of these previous global assessments accounts for floods. This is particularly problematic
51 as the evidence for a relation between climate change and the changes in TC wind speeds
52 (or pressure) is rather weak and subject to large uncertainties^{22,23}. By contrast, the risk of
53 TC-induced flooding is clearly expected to increase under climate change: Sea level rise will
54 amplify the risk of coastal flooding, and increasingly heavy precipitation will increase the

55 risk of pluvial and fluvial flooding²⁴.

56 Global studies that estimate the number of people affected by TC-related storm surge^{25,26}
57 use stylized modeling approaches to generate the floodplains, compared to the advanced
58 physics-based frameworks used in local studies¹⁴. Thus, not incorporating flooding as a
59 driver of damages, or not including all drivers of flooding (pluvial, fluvial, and surge) and
60 their compound effects, seriously limits the usefulness of the available global assessments.
61 A sound understanding of TC impacts is key to i) estimate which damages in the historical
62 period can already be attributed to climate change (impact attribution) and ii) obtain more
63 reliable projections of future damages under climate and socioeconomic change (impact
64 projections).

65 Here we only focus on coastal flooding. As observational data on flood affected areas are
66 only available for a limited set of TCs, various approaches have been developed to simulate
67 the historical flood extents. Since flow solvers are often optimized to model either large-scale
68 ocean dynamics, or small-scale estuaries and overland flooding, uncoupling the coastal surge
69 processes from the coastal inundation is a common approach to coastal flood modeling²⁶. Es-
70 pecially for multi-storm assessments, a two-step approach can reduce computational demand
71 and data requirements: In the first step, ocean models such as ADCIRC²⁷, COMCOT²⁸,
72 Delft3D FM²⁹, FVCOM³⁰, MIKE21³¹, POM³², ROMS³³, SLOSH³⁴, or TELEMAC³⁵ consider
73 effects of the atmosphere, astronomical tides, and waves on hydrodynamics to produce time
74 series of water levels along the coastlines, called hydrographs³⁶. The hydrographs computed
75 with an ocean model are, in the second modeling step, used as an input for an inland flood
76 model that translates them into inundated areas. A common simple flood modeling approach
77 on the global scale is based on static (so-called planar, GIS-based, or bathtub-type) inun-
78 dation models, such as the one used in the World Resources Institute's Aqueduct project³⁷.
79 Static, bathtub-type approaches assume that any grid point is inundated if it has an eleva-
80 tion less than the extreme water level, usually attenuated according to its distance to the
81 coastline. In case studies, static approaches have been shown to underestimate flooding and
82 the importance of using dynamic approaches was emphasized frequently³⁸⁻⁴¹. However, the
83 studies had a very local scope and were based on a comparably small amount of observational
84 data. In regional assessments, more computationally expensive dynamic flood models⁴² go-
85 ing beyond the static approaches were used: CaMa-Flood⁴³ is a river-routing model that
86 resolves large-scale one-dimensional discharge along river networks. LISFLOOD-FP⁴⁴ and

87 SFINCS⁴⁵ model two-dimensional floodplain flow over land using different simplified versions
88 of the shallow-water equations (SWEs), without atmospheric forcing, Coriolis, and viscosity
89 terms. Since SFINCS is able to incorporate an advection and wind drag term, it can also
90 model some of the processes from the first (ocean-modeling) step. HEC-RAS⁴⁶ models one-
91 or two-dimensional riverine flows using variants of the SWEs. These dynamic flood models
92 can be used to model coastal inundation processes, with river discharge as upstream and
93 ocean models as downstream boundary conditions⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹.

94 Beyond the two-step approaches, some of the dynamic models listed above have been used
95 to model ocean dynamics and coastal inundation in a single step, e.g. using ADCIRC⁵⁰. And
96 even though there have been major advancements in computational demand recently⁵¹, the
97 focus of those studies has been on a single event or on a small region. On the other hand,
98 studies with a global scope only considered peak storm tides and not the flood extents so
99 far⁵²⁻⁵⁵. A recent global study uses Delft3D to compute surge-induced flooding for a large
100 database of historical TCs for 10 km grid cells that are contiguous to the coast⁵⁶. While this
101 is a huge effort and a major step forward in TC surge modeling, the data is only validated
102 with peak storm tides⁵⁷ instead of observational flood extents or field measurements, and
103 the coarse resolution limits the explanatory power of the results. An example for a static
104 one-step approach is the storm surge module implemented in the open-source risk assessment
105 toolbox CLIMADA⁵⁸. In this approach, the inundation height in each grid cell is estimated
106 from wind speed, distance to coast, and topographical elevation using a linear relationship⁵⁹.
107 More recently, machine learning-based methods that do not rely on ocean models have been
108 developed to generate synthetic storm tide hydrographs^{60,61}, peak storm tides at a small
109 selection of points⁶²⁻⁶⁴, or even gridded flood extents⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷ for risk analyses. However, the
110 field of machine learning-based flood area and depth assessment is in an early stage and all
111 the existing models are only calibrated for comparably small regions.

112 In this study, we introduce a globally applicable, event-based and dynamic one-step ap-
113 proach, building on the intermediate-complexity geophysical flow solver GeoClaw^{68,69}. Solv-
114 ing the depth-averaged shallow water equations, GeoClaw allows us to seamlessly model
115 TC-induced surges (hydrographs) and inundated areas along coastlines (Fig. 1), at an in-
116 termediate spatial resolution that is higher than global-scale ocean models but lower than
117 most coastal inundation models. In contrast to static, not process-based (e.g. bathtub-type)
118 approaches, GeoClaw accounts for the event-specific variation of wind and pressure over

Fig. 1. Overview of the considered modeling frameworks. The four different approaches to modeling coastal flood extents from tropical cyclone storm surge: Use hydrographs generated by the dynamic ocean model GTSM (dotted arrows) or GeoClaw (dashed arrows) as input for the static inundation model Aqueduct; directly obtain the flood extents from the dynamic ocean model GeoClaw (bold arrows); estimate flood extents from the statistical intensity-surge relationship implemented in CLIMADA (solid arrows).

119 time as well as for run-up of waves and overland flow around obstacles. But GeoClaw’s
120 complexity is moderate compared to many flood models as it does not incorporate dynamic
121 interactions with astronomical tides, short surface gravity waves (wind sea and swell), river
122 discharge, or spatially varying surface friction characteristics over land. Since astronomical
123 tides cannot be imposed as dynamic boundary conditions in GeoClaw, we instead add a
124 constant offset to the zero water level of the ocean at rest that is derived from astronomical
125 tides in a preprocessing step to each simulation run.

126 Even though our approach does not incorporate some of the dynamic drivers of inunda-
127 tion (e.g. astronomical tides or river discharge), our modeling provides strong indications
128 that modeling inundation dynamics is important for accurately reproducing observed flood
129 extents. To this end, we compare four modeling approaches (Fig. 1): (1) GeoClaw, (2) a
130 combination of GeoClaw with the static inundation model of the World Resources Institute’s
131 Aqueduct project³⁷ (GeoClaw+Aqueduct), (3) a combination of the Global Tide and Surge
132 Model (GTSM)⁷⁰, which is built around the ocean dynamics model Delft3D FM, with the
133 static Aqueduct model (GTSM+Aqueduct), and (4) the static inundation model included
134 in CLIMADA as a light-weight approach used for large-scale risk assessments (CLIMADA).
135 The second and third (GeoClaw+Aqueduct and GTSM+Aqueduct) are two-step approaches,
136 and the first and last approach (GeoClaw and CLIMADA) are one-step approaches. The
137 two-step GeoClaw+Aqueduct approach has not been used in the literature before, and we
138 only include it here to illustrate the role of inundation dynamics in the one-step GeoClaw
139 approach. The GTSM+Aqueduct approach is a state-of-the-art two-step approach for global
140 assessments^{25,37,71,72}. All models are configured to use the same global digital elevation model
141 (DEM) dataset at 1 km resolution (Methods). As the primary output of our approach are
142 inundated land areas, we focus our main analysis on this quantity. We apply the models
143 to a global set of 71 storms between 2000 and 2019 and evaluate their performance in re-
144 producing satellite-based observations of coastal inundated areas. We only include low-lying
145 grid cells with a height of between 0 and 10 meters above geoid, and outside of permanent
146 water bodies, in order to reduce the share of flooded areas that are due to pluvial and fluvial
147 floods (see Methods for a detailed description of the observational datasets). In addition,
148 we evaluate coastal high water marks which are available for 8 U.S. storms (Fig. 2 and
149 [Supplementary Tbls. S1 to S3](#)).

Fig. 2. Overview of the observational validation data. **a** The validation data includes 97 flood extents (red boxes) for 71 distinct tropical cyclone events. For 34 of the storms, tide gauge measurements are available. In total, 383 tide gauge time series at 213 distinct tide gauge stations (black dots) are used. **b** For 11 storms in the USA and Puerto Rico, a total of 1007 field measurements of inundation heights (high water marks; orange dots) are available. **c** The events cover the period 2000–2019, and all intensities of the Saffir-Simpson Hurricane Scale (color scale).

150 Results

151 Evaluation of modeled inundated areas

152 The inundated areas calculated with GeoClaw by dynamically and spatially resolving the
 153 inundation processes based on the physics of fluid dynamics are substantially larger and
 154 reproduce observed flood extents better than the two static (not process-based) inundation
 155 models.

156 We first consider the showcases of Hurricane Harvey (August 2017, Fig. 3) and Hurricane
 157 Rita (September 2005, Fig. 4), which made landfall on similar geographical regions in Texas
 158 and Louisiana. Both storms caused a significant storm surge, but the compound effects of
 159 rainfall and surge played a major role for Hurricane Harvey⁷³, while the impact of Hurricane
 160 Rita was dominated by a devastating storm surge and comparably moderate amounts of
 161 rainfall⁷⁴. For each of the events, satellite-based flood extents are available from two different

Fig. 3. Observed and simulated flood extents for Hurricane Harvey (2017). The flood extents from two different satellite-based observations (**a** RAPID and **b** DFO) as well as from four inundation models (**c–f**) are shown, covering an 800 km stretch of coast line from Corpus Christi (Texas) in the west, via Galveston (Texas), to New Orleans (Louisiana) in the east. Some areas are marked as missing (gray) in the satellite-based products. Permanent water bodies (blue) as well as areas with an elevation of more than 10 meters above geoid (black) were excluded from the analysis. Wet (flooded) areas are marked in brown and dry (non-flooded) areas are marked in white. All products are reprojected to the same 1 km grid for comparison. In the model outputs, a grid cell is marked as flooded if the simulated flood depth exceeds 0.1 m.

Fig. 4. Observed and simulated flood extents for Hurricane Rita (2005). The flood extents from two different satellite-based observations (a GFD and b DFO) as well as from four inundation models (c–f) are shown, covering an 800 km stretch of coast line from Victoria (Texas) in the west, via Galveston (Texas), to New Orleans (Louisiana) and Gulfport (Louisiana) in the east. Some areas are marked as missing (gray) in the satellite-based products. Permanent water bodies (blue) as well as areas with an elevation of more than 10 meters above geoid (black) were excluded from the analysis. Wet (flooded) areas are marked in brown and dry (non-flooded) areas are marked in white. All products are reprojected to the same 1 km grid for comparison. In the model outputs, a grid cell is marked as flooded if the simulated flood depth exceeds 0.1 m.

Fig. 5. Comparison statistics for satellite-based flood extents. **a-c** Three metrics (higher is better) are used to express the overall performance of inundation models in reproducing the observed flood extents for 71 storm events. **d** The ratio of true negative areas (TNR) expresses the share of areas correctly classified as dry (higher is better) – an aspect that is not covered by the F1 and F2 performance scores (panels b and c). **e** The bias score expresses the tendency of a model to over- (positive values) or underpredict (negative values). Note the logarithmic scaling on the y-axis with linear scaling between -1 and 1. The evaluation can either be done for each flood map separately, resulting in a range of score values for each of the models (map-by-map score; colored boxes), or across all grid cells contained in all flood maps, resulting in a single performance score for each of the models (total score; black stars). The boxes denote the interquartile ranges with a horizontal black line for the median value, whiskers for the 95% intervals, and circles for the minimum and maximum values.

162 observational sources. GeoClaw’s inundated areas reach relatively far inland while static,
 163 bathtub-type models merely inundate a shallow strip of the coastline. Though there are
 164 substantial differences between satellite observations (Figs. 3a and 3b, Figs. 4a and 4b) and
 165 all models (Figs. 3c to 3f, Figs. 4c to 4f), the inundated areas calculated dynamically with
 166 GeoClaw reach relatively far inland (Figs. 3c and 4c) and are closer to the observed extents
 167 than those obtained with the static, not process-based approaches (CLIMADA, Figs. 3d
 168 and 4d, and GTSM+Aqueduct, Figs. 3f and 4f). The narrow coastal inundation of static
 169 models also holds when we drive the static, bathtub-type Aqueduct model with the time
 170 series of coastal water levels (hydrographs) produced by GeoClaw (GeoClaw+Aqueduct,
 171 Figs. 3e and 4e). This gives us a first indication that the different characteristics of the
 172 modeled flooded areas between GeoClaw and the static modeling approaches could result
 173 from the dynamical modeling of the inundation processes in GeoClaw.

174 The inundated areas calculated with GeoClaw match the satellite-observations better
 175 than those from static inundation models. To see this, we first classify each cell of the

Tbl. 1. Performance indicators for the evaluation of flood extents (total scores and medians of map-by-map scores, separated by \star , with interquartile range in parentheses, Fig. 5). For 95% intervals and minima/maxima, see Supplementary Tbl. S4.

Model	MCC	F1	F2	TNR (%)	Bias
GeoClaw	+0.22 \star +0.10 (+0.04 - +0.21)	0.34 \star 0.15 (0.07 - 0.28)	0.20 \star 0.08 (0.04 - 0.16)	89% \star 93% (87% - 98%)	-0.22 \star -0.18 (-1.51 - +0.72)
GeoClaw+Aqueduct	+0.11 \star +0.04 (+0.00 - +0.08)	0.13 \star 0.03 (0.00 - 0.08)	0.07 \star 0.01 (0.00 - 0.04)	98% \star 99% (98% - 100%)	-1.65 \star -2.77 (-5.27 - -0.80)
GTSM+Aqueduct	+0.10 \star +0.06 (+0.00 - +0.11)	0.12 \star 0.04 (0.01 - 0.12)	0.06 \star 0.02 (0.00 - 0.07)	98% \star 99% (97% - 100%)	-1.74 \star -1.95 (-3.77 - -0.39)
CLIMADA	+0.09 \star +0.05 (+0.00 - +0.11)	0.18 \star 0.05 (0.01 - 0.19)	0.10 \star 0.03 (0.00 - 0.10)	94% \star 97% (95% - 100%)	-0.86 \star -1.47 (-3.24 - +0.12)

176 flood maps for the full set of 71 TCs as either “wet” (positive) or “dry” (negative). We then
177 use three performance metrics (scores, see Methods) calculated from the areas classified as
178 true positive, true negative, false positive and false negative⁷⁵: As the harmonic mean of
179 precision and recall, the F1 score (with values between 0 and 1) is a metric for the accuracy
180 of a prediction[76]. The F2 score (with values between 0 and 1) is the ratio of the area
181 classified as wet by both (model and observation) divided by the area classified as wet by
182 any of the two[77]. Despite being the predominant indicators of model performance, these
183 scores are known to be biased in favor of overpredictions[78]. For this reason, we additionally
184 consider the Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), also known as (Yule) Phi coefficient.
185 MCC is the Pearson correlation coefficient estimated for two binary variables (with values
186 between -1 and 1). It is generally regarded as a more informative and true score if the class
187 sizes (here the areas of “wet” and “dry” cells) vary[79] (see Methods for a detailed discussion
188 of the different performance indicators).

189 GeoClaw outperforms the static, not process-based approaches for all three performance
190 scores (Fig. 5 and Tbl. 1). This finding remains robust also if instead of the map-by-map score
191 which results in a range of score values (colored boxes with black horizontal lines indicating
192 median values in Fig. 5), we consider all floods at once which results in a single performance
193 score for each model (total score; black stars in Fig. 5). All flood maps contribute equally to
194 the map-by-map score whereas the influence of flood maps on the total score increases with
195 their geographical area.

196 Inundated areas calculated dynamically with GeoClaw are larger than those obtained
197 with static, not process-based models. To see this, we consider the ratio of true negative
198 areas (TNR). A low TNR indicates that a prediction tends to overpredict, but underpredic-
199 tion is not penalized (classifying all cells as dry yields a perfect TNR of 100%). Further, we
200 consider the bias score which weighs overpredictions (too many wet cells) against underpre-
201 dictions (too many dry cells). A positive (negative) bias indicates a tendency to overpredict
202 (underpredict). The TNR of GeoClaw (93%) is much lower than the TNR of the static inun-
203 dation models (99% for GTSM+Aqueduct, and 97% for CLIMADA). The comparably high
204 TNR of the latter suggests that the static inundation models underestimate the floodplains.
205 This is also confirmed by the strongly negative biases of these models with median values
206 ranging from -1.95 (GTSM+Aqueduct) to -1.47 (CLIMADA), whereas the bias of the inun-
207 dated areas calculated with GeoClaw is much closer to zero (-0.18). While it is beyond the
208 scope of this analysis to understand the exact reasons why GeoClaw underpredicts the inun-
209 dated areas, we note that a tendency to underpredict would be expected because GeoClaw
210 does not account for pluvial and fluvial floods. As for the case of Hurricane Harvey, cou-
211 pling the hydrographs obtained with GeoClaw with the static inundation model Aqueduct
212 (GeoClaw+Aqueduct) yields a systematic underprediction of inundated areas (99% TNR
213 and -2.77 bias) which is similar to the other static approaches. As all models use the same
214 topographic dataset, this indicates that the underestimation of inundated areas by the static
215 models is caused by a systematic failure to represent some of the dynamic processes modeled
216 by GeoClaw.

217 Across all basins, GeoClaw outperforms the static inundation models (Fig. 6). In our
218 analysis, we distinguish three regions of TC activity, one for the southern hemisphere (SH)
219 and two for the northern hemisphere: the North Atlantic and eastern North Pacific (AP),
220 and the western North Pacific and northern Indian Ocean (PI). Without taking landfall and
221 flood characteristics into account, approximately one third of global TC activity is located in
222 each of the three regions. However, in our flood extent data, SH is under-represented (20%,
223 14 storms), and AP is over-represented (46%, 33 storms), each by approximately 40%. Model
224 performance is generally higher in AP than in the other two regions, with the exception of
225 GTSM+Aqueduct that performs in PI better than in AP.

226 So far, we have used satellite-based flood maps to compare the performance of GeoClaw
227 in comparison to static inundation models because, for many storms, this data is the only

Fig. 6. Evaluation of model performance by world region. The performance scores of modeled flood extents are shown for each of three world regions North Atlantic and eastern North Pacific (AP, a–e), western North Pacific and northern Indian Ocean (PI, f–j), and the southern hemisphere (SH, k–o). The colored boxes denote the interquartile ranges with a horizontal black line for the median value, whiskers for the 95% intervals, circles for the minimum and maximum values, and a black star for the total score. For a detailed description of the panels in each row, see Fig. 5.

228 available systematic observational information about flood extents. However, satellite-based
229 observations come with some important shortcomings limiting their suitability for storm
230 surge model evaluations. Most importantly, the inundated areas may not only result from
231 storm surge but also from pluvial floods and river floods. This renders it a priori difficult to
232 decide whether the, on average, larger inundated areas obtained by GeoClaw are indeed more
233 realistic than those of the static approaches or whether GeoClaw “accidentally” performs
234 better because it overestimates the extents of the storm surges and thus partially replaces the
235 missing flood drivers. To limit this risk, we restrict our analysis to low-lying (less than 10 m)
236 areas and consider performance metrics that account for both over- and underpredictions.
237 Note, however, that this reduces, but does not remove the influence of confounding drivers
238 completely since the low-lying areas still experience flooding from confounding drivers, as in
239 the case of Hurricane Harvey (Fig. 3)⁴.

240 Satellite-based flood maps tend to underestimate the flooded areas because satellites can
241 only detect water bodies that persist until the satellite flies over the given area⁸⁰⁻⁸². More-
242 over, even in cases where timely coverage is available, there is evidence that satellite-based
243 flood extents can suffer from both under- and over-predictions^{83,84}. Due to this potential
244 underestimation of the inundated areas by satellite-based products, the inundation models
245 could underestimate the low-lying inundated areas even more strongly than already sug-
246 gested by our performance analysis (Fig. 5 and Tbl. 1). Finally, comparing the flood extents
247 as obtained from different satellite observations, we find that the disagreement between ob-
248 servational products is quite substantial (Supplementary Fig. S2 and Supplementary Note
249 1). This indicates that satellite-based observations do not reach the quality of ground based
250 observations which introduces an additional uncertainty dimension into our evaluation exer-
251 cise.

252 **Comparison of modeled inundated areas with high water marks**

253 To gain a better understanding whether the satellite-based and modelled inundated areas
254 over- or underestimate the actual storm surge-affected areas, we additionally compare them
255 to field measurements of inundation heights (high water marks, HWMs) from the US Ge-
256 ological Survey (USGS) Short-Term Network (STN)⁸⁵ (see Methods). This dataset covers
257 1007 coastal HWMs for 11 TCs which made landfall in the USA out of the ensemble of 71

Fig. 7. High water mark and tide gauge measurements for Hurricane Harvey (2017). **a** Inundation heights (color scale) above ground for 135 coastal high water mark locations (diamonds) along the Texas coast, measured in the aftermath of Hurricane Harvey in August 2017. **b** Maximum water levels (color scale) measured at 34 tide gauge locations (circles) and simulated at 42 additional output locations (squares). **c–e** Measured and simulated water level time series (hydrographs) at Packery Channel (**c**), High Island (**d**), and Freshwater Canal Locks (**e**) tide gauge stations.

Fig. 8. High water mark and tide gauge measurements for Hurricane Rita (2005). **a** Inundation heights (color scale) above ground for 6 coastal high water mark locations (diamonds) along the Texas coast, measured in the aftermath of Hurricane Rita in September 2005. **b** Maximum water levels (color scale) measured at 5 tide gauge locations (circles) and simulated at 32 additional output locations (squares). **c–e** Measured and simulated water level time series (hydrographs) at Freeport (**c**), and Galveston Pier 21 (**d**) tide gauge stations, and at the GTSM output location with ID 15356 (**e**).

Fig. 9. Comparison with high water marks (HWMs). **a** The share of HWMs for 11 storms in the USA and Puerto Rico where the satellite observations (white) and the inundation models (other colors) correctly classify a location as wet (hit rate). **b** Comparison of surface elevation and inundation heights recorded at HWMs to our digital elevation model (green box) and to the inundation models (other colors). Note the logarithmic scaling of the y-axis with linear scaling between -1 and 1. Colored boxes denote interquartile ranges with a black horizontal line for the median value, whiskers for 95% intervals, and circles for the minimum and maximum values.

258 studied storms, including Hurricane Harvey and Hurricane Rita (Figs. 7a, 8a and 9). As
 259 field measurements, they do not suffer the potential biases of the satellite-based data. Fur-
 260 ther, since HWMs come with a classification as coastal or riverine, we restrict our analysis
 261 to coastal locations to ensure that the recorded flood was predominantly caused by storm
 262 surge.

263 The tendency of satellite observations to underestimate flood extents is confirmed when
 264 considering HWMs. In fact, only 88% of the 1007 HWM locations are marked as wet in
 265 at least one of the satellite-based flood maps (white box in Fig. 9a). GeoClaw outperforms
 266 static approaches concerning the hit-rate of flooded HWM locations. It estimates inunda-
 267 tion for 92% of the HWM locations. CLIMADA (79%) and GTSM+Aqueduct (78%) score
 268 lower in predicting the flooded HWM locations (Fig. 9a and Supplementary Tbl. S5). As for
 269 the satellite-based flood extents, the agreement of the inundated areas calculated by Geo-
 270 Claw+Aqueduct with the HWMs is lower (79%) than for the one-step GeoClaw approach
 271 (92%). This provides another indication that dynamically resolving the inundation processes
 272 is critical for a better representation of observed surge areas. Notably, both GeoClaw and
 273 satellite-observations underestimate flood extents. This could hint that, also for the full en-
 274 semble of 71 storms, the comparably better performance of GeoClaw compared to the static
 275 inundation models may not result from an overestimation of the surge affected areas.

276 GeoClaw underestimates inundation heights, but with lower bias than the static mod-

277 els. In contrast to the satellite-observations, the HWMs allow us to evaluate the inundation
278 heights provided by the inundation models. All models differ from the HWM inundation
279 heights by more than a meter (considering both under- and overestimation), but with quite
280 different biases. For 896 among the 1007 HWMs, GeoClaw has non-zero inundation heights.
281 GeoClaw somewhat underestimates the inundation heights (mean and median errors: 1.51 m
282 and 1.16 m; interquartile range (IQR): 0.57 m–2.02 m; average bias: -0.49 m). The under-
283 estimation of inundation heights by the static inundation models (GeoClaw+Aqueduct:
284 $N = 772$; mean and median errors: 1.80 m and 1.46 m; IQR: 0.69–2.42 m; average bias -
285 0.88 m), GTSM+Aqueduct ($N = 762$; mean and median errors: 1.90 m and 1.42 m; IQR:
286 0.78 m–2.65 m; average bias -1.07 m), and CLIMADA ($N = 772$; mean and median errors:
287 1.61 m and 1.15 m; IQR: 0.49 m–2.15 m; average bias: -0.76 m) is even larger (Fig. 9b and
288 [Supplementary Tbl. S5](#)).

289 Global Digital Elevation Model (DEM) biases are an important and often dominant
290 source of uncertainty. Comparing the height information of the DEM used in this study
291 with the ground elevation recorded at 666 of the 1007 HWMs shows that the elevations in
292 the DEM tend to be too low (average bias of -1.44 m; IQR: -2.67 m – -0.02 m; green box in
293 [Fig. 9b](#) and [Supplementary Tbl. S5](#)). For 50% of the HWM locations, the DEM deviates
294 from the recorded elevations by more than 1.80 m. For 140 HWMs (21%), the overestimation
295 of topographical heights in the DEM is higher than the actual inundation height. This means
296 that the DEM error is so high that even with the true hydrograph, any static, bathtub-type
297 inundation model would fail to predict flooding at these locations. Note, however, that this
298 analysis is only valid for the US coastal areas for which we have HWMs, and cannot easily
299 be translated to the global scope.

300 **Evaluation of coastal water levels**

301 So far our analyses have provided several indications that resolving the inundation dynamics
302 — as done by GeoClaw — could be critical to obtain larger floodplains which better agree
303 with observed surge affected areas than the floodplains obtained with static, not process-
304 based models. However, there is still the possibility that GeoClaw produces larger floodplains
305 because it overestimates coastal hydrographs. We next test this hypothesis.

306 For the example of Hurricane Harvey, GeoClaw does not systematically overestimate

Fig. 10. Comparison of observed with modeled hydrographs. We compare hydrographs observed at tide gauge stations with hydrographs simulated by GeoClaw (blue boxes) or by the state-of-the-art ocean model GTSM (orange boxes). We also compare the simulated hydrographs by GeoClaw with the GTSM simulations (boxes with blue and orange hatching). We compare (a) the absolute and signed deviations of maximum sea levels, and (b) the surge dynamics, using the performance metrics Pearson (higher is better) and RMSE (lower is better). The colored boxes denote interquartile ranges with a black horizontal line for the median value, whiskers for the 95% intervals, and circles for the minimum and maximum values. In panel a, note the logarithmic y-axis scaling with linear scaling between -1 and 1.

307 surge levels. We first compare observational and modeled hydrographs for Hurricane Harvey
 308 for hourly measurements of 34 tide gauge stations from GESLA3⁸⁶ (circles in Fig. 7b). The
 309 GeoClaw simulation, driven by a storm track from the IBTrACS archive (event number
 310 2017228N14314)⁸⁷, underestimates the observed maximum surge height relative to the geoid
 311 by 0.33 m on average and the mean absolute deviation of maximum sea levels is 0.50 m.
 312 Similarly, GTSM underestimates maximum surge heights by 0.28 m on average, but the
 313 mean absolute deviations of maximum surge heights are significantly better (0.36 m). Which
 314 model performs better differs from station to station and sometimes both models are rather
 315 close and other times far off the observations (cf. tide gauge stations Packery Channel,
 316 Fig. 3c, High Island, Fig. 3d, and Freshwater Canal Locks, Fig. 3e). For the example of
 317 Hurricane Rita, the number of available tide gauge records (only 5 stations) is too low for
 318 aggregate statistics (Fig. 8b). Also, the few available tide gauge stations (Figs. 8c and 8d) are
 319 relatively far away from the areas that were most affected according to the GTSM simulations
 320 (Fig. 8e).

321 For the set of available tide gauge observations, GeoClaw does not reach the accuracy of
 322 the state-of-the-art dynamic ocean model GTSM. In total, we can compare the simulated
 323 hydrographs to 383 observed hydrographs at 213 distinct tide gauge stations covering 34 out
 324 of the 71 studied TCs. GeoClaw does not reproduce coastal hydrographs with high accuracy

325 (mean and median absolute deviations of maximum sea levels are 0.50 m and 0.42 m; IQR:
326 0.23 m – 0.66 m; mean and median Pearson correlation coefficients of 0.50 and 0.66; IQR:
327 0.37 m – 0.82 m; mean and median RMSE of 0.24 m and 0.20 m; IQR: 0.12 m – 0.31 m;
328 **Figs. 10a and 10b and Supplementary Tbl. S5**). GTSM performs better in reproducing the
329 observed hydrographs than GeoClaw (mean and median absolute deviations of maximum
330 sea levels of 0.32 m and 0.26 m; IQR: 0.13 m – 0.42 m; mean and median Pearson correlation
331 coefficients of 0.65 and 0.82; IQR: 0.50 – 0.92; mean and median RMSE of 0.19 m and 0.15 m;
332 IQR: 0.10 m – 0.24 m). However, the improvement GTSM provides compared to GeoClaw is
333 moderate given that GeoClaw does not incorporate tidal dynamics or meteorological forcings
334 other than the parametric TC wind and pressure fields. This might in part be due to the
335 fact that GTSM is run at a lower resolution than our GeoClaw setup (Methods). Moreover,
336 GTSM is forced by wind fields from a reanalysis product that has been demonstrated to
337 underestimate TC wind speeds^{88,89}. The parametric wind fields used in our GeoClaw setup
338 are often asserted to be a more reliable input for storm surge simulations^{13,25,90,91}. While a
339 comparison of the models with identical resolution and wind forcing would be interesting,
340 this is beyond the scope of this work.

341 Notably, both models underestimate surge heights; the signed differences of observed and
342 modeled maximal surge heights have a bias of about 0.2 m (GeoClaw: -0.22 m; IQR: -0.57 m
343 – +0.10 m; GTSM: -0.21 m; IQR: -0.40 m – +0.00 m). Thus, the larger surge affected areas
344 obtained with GeoClaw compared to static, not process-based approaches are a result of the
345 dynamical modeling of the inundation dynamics and not due to a systematic overestimation
346 of coastal hydrographs. Further, the comparably better agreement between the inundated
347 areas calculated with GeoClaw and both satellite-based observations and HWMs shows that
348 its ability to resolve the inundation dynamics overcompensates for its lower performance in
349 reproducing observed hydrographs compared to the two-step approach of GTSM+Aqueduct.

350 Discussion

351 Recent studies have suggested ever higher mesh resolutions, more complex models, and high-
352 resolution DEMs as key factors for floodplain modeling⁹², which are accompanied by a drastic
353 increase in time, expertise and computing power required. These can limit the applicability
354 of these approaches for global risk assessments where large ensembles of (potential) storm

355 surge events have to be modelled.

356 Here, we have tested the performance of an intermediate-complexity approach based on
357 the geophysical flow solver GeoClaw. Having moderate data requirements and computa-
358 tional demands, the approach is placed between high resolution flood models and a much
359 simpler statistical modeling approach for inundated areas such as the coastal flood module
360 included in CLIMADA. Therefore, GeoClaw is popular among tsunami modelers for proba-
361 bilistic applications with large ensembles of inundation scenarios⁹³. In contrast to most other
362 approaches used for global storm surge modeling, GeoClaw allows to dynamically resolve the
363 inundation dynamics with a physics-based flow model (Methods).

364 Considering a global set of 71 TCs, we could show that GeoClaw consistently outperforms
365 a state-of-the-art global approach combining the computationally expensive ocean model
366 GTSM with the bathtub-type inundation model Aqueduct as well as the light-weight static
367 approach implemented in CLIMADA. We further traced the better performance of GeoClaw
368 back to its internal hydrodynamics. By dynamically resolving inundation processes, GeoClaw
369 can overcompensate the lower quality of its coastal surge height modeling in comparison to
370 GTSM. Furthermore, the dynamic model setup allows the use of the duration of flood events
371 in risk assessments, which is not possible with static inundation models.

372 For the calculation of inundated areas, GeoClaw does not rely on pre-computed global
373 ocean model outputs, which are known to underestimate TCs⁷⁰. Therefore, GeoClaw can be
374 used more flexibly for tailored assessments of TC surge impacts. Further, the moderate com-
375 putational resources required to run the model allow to calculate inundated areas for large
376 ensembles of synthetic storm tracks. Ensemble-based approaches have been used in recent
377 assessments of climate risks arising from changes in tropical cyclone climatology with global
378 warming^{17,20}. Such risk assessments are urgently needed to provide critical information and
379 decision support for the Loss and Damage debate⁹⁴ at the international climate negotiations
380 as well as by national actors charged with the development and implementations of the Na-
381 tional Adaptation Plans⁹⁵. While country- or state-level negotiators usually do not have the
382 expertise to run GeoClaw for own assessments, interdisciplinary research teams will be able
383 to base global tropical cyclone assessments on our approach. Some country-level assessments
384 are already based on more advanced modeling approaches, but for globally consistent as-
385 sessments, there is still demand for an approach of intermediate complexity. Further, our
386 approach is well suited for climate attribution studies. For instance, GeoClaw was recently

387 used to estimate the contribution of climate change to the human displacements in the af-
388 termath of Cyclone Idai, which made landfall in Mozambique in March 2019, accounting for
389 sea level rise and changes in storm intensity due to global warming¹⁴. In that study, external
390 sea level rise information was integrated into GeoClaw as an adjustment of the zero water
391 level.

392 However, the model setup used in this study is subject to several limitations (cf. Meth-
393 ods). Currently, GeoClaw is not able to integrate dynamical astronomical tides at the open
394 ocean boundaries, pluvial flooding from surface runoff, or fluvial flooding from discharge at
395 the inland upstream boundaries of rivers. Further, GeoClaw allows to model only one TC at
396 a time, and cannot account for the influence of sequential TCs⁹⁶ or interactions with mon-
397 soon rainfall⁹⁷. This is particularly important since sequential TCs are projected to occur
398 more often under climate change⁹⁸, in line with an increase in multiple TC events⁹⁹. Some
399 of these issues affect properties of the implementation and not of the conceptual design of
400 GeoClaw, and could be added relatively easily to GeoClaw in the future.

401 Further, ideally, the interaction between surge, fluvial, and pluvial drivers are simulated
402 as well to account for compound impact of all three drivers. Such compound effects played
403 for instance a crucial role in the case of Harvey^{3,4}. In this sense, it would be interesting to
404 compare a global set of observational data of TC events such as the one presented in this
405 study with a number of more complex ocean models or compound flood models that are able
406 to take more aspects of flooding into account than the GeoClaw setup that we used here.

407 **Methods**

408 **Overview**

409 The four approaches to estimate coastal flood extents from TCs that are compared in this
410 study are a combination of the four models GeoClaw, GTSM, Aqueduct, and CLIMADA
411 (Fig. 1). We describe the models and their respective input and output data in the following
412 subsections. Here, we provide an overview of the approaches and data.

413 Our proposed model setup with GeoClaw produces flood extents from TC storm track
414 data. The CLIMADA modeling approach uses the same input data and produces the same
415 kind of output data, but does not resolve any flow dynamics. The other two approaches

416 GTSM+Aqueduct and GeoClaw+Aqueduct are a combination of a dynamic ocean model
417 (GeoClaw or GTSM) with the static inundation model Aqueduct: Coastal hydrographs are
418 computed as an intermediate data product that is used by Aqueduct to translate peak storm
419 tides at the coast into flood extents using a bathtub-type method.

420 Model runs of GeoClaw, Aqueduct, and CLIMADA have been conducted for this study.
421 For GTSM, we used publicly available model outputs⁷⁰. GeoClaw, Aqueduct and CLIMADA
422 use the same topo-bathymetric data set, while GTSM uses GEBCO¹⁰⁰. Moreover, while
423 GeoClaw and CLIMADA use wind and pressure forcing derived from TC track data using
424 parametric models, the meteorological forcing for GTSM is taken from reanalysis data.

425 Both dynamic models (GeoClaw and GTSM) are based on the two-dimensional depth-
426 averaged shallow water equations (SWEs). Both use finite volume methods to solve the
427 equations, but while GeoClaw uses structured (rectangular) grids, unstructured (curvilinear)
428 grids are used in GTSM. In both models, the spatial resolution increases in coastal areas,
429 starting from a 25 km resolution over the open ocean. GTSM uses a fixed, pre-computed grid,
430 with a resolution of up to 2.5 km, while GeoClaw uses adaptive mesh refinement to increase
431 the grid resolution locally during run time to up to 0.25 km. GTSM uses the globe as a single
432 model domain and runs for the whole period 1979–2017. For GeoClaw, independent runs
433 encompassing 48 hours each and a storm-specific geographical domain are set up for each
434 individual storm. While GTSM models only ocean cells with shearless free-slip boundary
435 conditions at coastlines, GeoClaw seamlessly models coastal inundation processes for land
436 cells. In GTSM, astronomical tides are included through tide generating forces. GeoClaw
437 is not able to model tidal forcing dynamical. Instead, we apply a static correction of the
438 zero water level, based on pre-computed astronomical tides. In both models, wind and
439 pressure are incorporated as forcing terms in the momentum equations, but different wind
440 and pressure data sets are used as input data.

441 While GeoClaw uses a physics-based description of bottom friction to model the coastal
442 inundation processes, the static models Aqueduct and CLIMADA use a simplified concept of
443 friction that assumes a linear decrease in flood height with distance from the coast. The rate
444 of decrease (resistance factor) is constant for CLIMADA, and depends on the topographic
445 terrain features for Aqueduct. The computational demands for the dynamic models GeoClaw
446 and GTSM are so high that a high-performance computing (HPC) cluster is necessary to run
447 the models at the 1 km resolution used in this study. Even then, computing the dynamics for

448 a single storm event can take several hours. The static models CLIMADA and Aqueduct,
449 on the other hand, can be run on a laptop computer with run times of less than a minute
450 for CLIMADA, or several minutes for Aqueduct.

451 Compared to regionally refined two-step approaches with dynamic ocean and inundation
452 models, the data requirements and computational demands of our GeoClaw-based approach
453 are moderate. However, it still requires substantially more time and expertise than CLI-
454 MADA. While Aqueduct is also comparably simple, it takes hydrographs from dynamic
455 ocean models as an input. The most important features that make our proposed GeoClaw-
456 based approach manageable: The software is open-source and available under a free license;
457 the input data is freely available for all global regions; the setup and configuration of GeoClaw
458 can be done in Python, even though the core of GeoClaw is written in Fortran; numerical
459 and model parameters do not require case-specific adjustments or calibrations; the mesh is
460 automatically adapted to the study region and event, and does not need to be pre-computed
461 and adjusted manually; when applying the approach to large ensembles of storms, only
462 the most intense ensemble members require long computational times, ensemble members
463 with low intensity require less computational time; a GPU-accelerated version of the code is
464 available, further decreasing run times if GPUs are available.

465 **Dynamic surge and inundation from GeoClaw**

466 We model surge heights and inundated areas using the open-source geophysical flow solver
467 GeoClaw that solves the depth-averaged shallow water equations (SWEs)⁶⁸. We configure
468 GeoClaw’s adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) feature to start with a 0.25 degree (25 km) grid
469 over the open ocean and refine the mesh in coastal areas to up to 9 arc-seconds (180-270
470 meters, depending on latitude), with five intermediate refinement levels. The resolution
471 over the open ocean thus agrees with the one used in the GTSM setup (see below). In
472 coastal areas, the resolution is higher than common global ocean model configurations: For
473 recent global hindcast data sets, GTSM was configured with 2.5 km resolution^{70,101}, and
474 SCHISM⁵² with 2 km resolution at the coastlines. As our model setup aims at an output
475 resolution of 1 km (30 arc-seconds), we selected the lower bound for the input resolution to
476 be slightly lower (9 arc-seconds) for numerical stability. Note that GeoClaw locally adjusts
477 the resolution automatically for each run, and 9 arc-seconds is only a lower bound.

478 The topo-bathymetric data used with GeoClaw is a combination of three global digital el-
479 evation models (DEMs). We use SRTM15+ (version 2.3) globally as the source of bathymetry
480 with a resolution of 0.5 km¹⁰², and the global CoastalDEM (version 2.1)¹⁰³ dataset for coastal
481 areas. CoastalDEM has a focus on coastal areas and comes at a resolution of 90 m. For the
482 land area that is not covered by CoastalDEM, we use MERIT-DEM¹⁰⁴. Since all three
483 DEM products (SRTM15+, CoastalDEM, MERIT-DEM) are already provided relative to
484 the same vertical datum (the Earth Gravitation Model from 1996, EGM96), we overlay
485 them without vertical adjustment. We first resample SRTM15+ from 15 to 3 arc-seconds
486 resolution to fit the resolution of MERIT-DEM and CoastalDEM. Then, we fill missing
487 values in MERIT-DEM with SRTM15+ (this mostly affects the bathymetry) and overlay
488 the result with CoastalDEM outside of permanent water bodies (as provided by ESRI on
489 <https://hub.arcgis.com/content/e750071279bf450cbd510454a80f2e63/>). Finally, we
490 resample the combined result to a resolution of 30 arc-seconds (approximately 900 m). This
491 smoothes out transitions between the different data sets while being sufficiently accurate in
492 the context of our inundation models that are configured to generate results at this reso-
493 lution. While high-resolution LiDAR DEMs are available for most of the US coastal areas
494 and several other regions (e.g. Australia), we decided to use global DEMs everywhere for
495 consistency. The applicability with globally harmonized data sets is a primary concern in
496 the design of our approach, since we aim at global assessments of climate risk. Also, the
497 handling of LiDAR DEMs can be challenging since they usually cover comparably small
498 regions and DEMs for neighboring regions are often not harmonized. We used the combined
499 land-ocean data set SRTM15+ for bathymetry instead of the pure ocean data set GEBCO¹⁰⁰
500 because the seamless transition from ocean to land is important in our one-step approach.
501 CoastalDEM is used because it is the best available global DEM for coastal modeling¹⁰⁵.
502 MERIT-DEM is used to fill small gaps in CoastalDEM since CoastalDEM does not cover
503 the whole land area, and SRTM15+ has lower resolution than MERIT-DEM. A comparison
504 with other choices of global DEMs would be an interesting topic for future research¹⁰⁶.

505 In a preprocessing step, we divide each storm into temporal periods (modeling periods) of
506 at most 48 hours. Due to the adjustment of zero water levels according to local astronomical
507 tidal conditions (see below), the period may not be too long since tidal conditions change over
508 time. On the other hand, the length must be sufficient for the spin-up of the wind-induced
509 flow dynamics. Those parts where the distance of the storm to the closest coast is larger

510 than twice the radius of maximum winds are excluded. GeoClaw is then started for each
 511 of the modeling periods separately. For each modeling period, the computational domain of
 512 the simulation is chosen to be large enough to accommodate the storm track together with
 513 a buffer of 2.5 times the radius of the outermost closed isobar.

514 Along the boundaries of the computational domain, GeoClaw uses extrapolation (non-
 515 reflecting or outgoing) boundary conditions that let the model waves from inside the model
 516 domain pass through the boundary without reflection. There is currently no way to impose
 517 dynamic water level boundary conditions according to astronomical tides. Instead, we set the
 518 zero water level (for the water body at rest) to the maximum astronomical tide attained in
 519 the center of the affected coastal area during each modeling period. Coastal areas are taken
 520 to be affected if the distance to the storm eye is not more than twice the radius of maximum
 521 winds. The astronomical tides are taken from the FES2014¹⁰⁷ simulations, referenced to
 522 a geoidal vertical datum using the gridded satellite altimetry product by AVISO¹⁰⁸. Since
 523 the satellite altimetry is relative to the geoid model GOCO05s, we further converted the
 524 heights to EGM96, the geoid model used in the global DEM datasets (see above). We
 525 use the maximum since our comparison with tide gauge measurements showed that the
 526 simulated surges tend to underestimate tide gauge observations even with this zero water
 527 level configuration. To demonstrate the sensitivity of our model setup to this setting, we
 528 show results for three different assumptions on the zero water level in [Supplementary Figs. S7](#)
 529 to [S9](#).

530 The flow dynamics are forced by wind speed W and air pressure P_A . GeoClaw derives
 531 this information on-the-fly from observed parameters along a storm track data set using the
 532 Holland 1980 parametric wind and pressure model¹⁰⁹:

$$W = \sqrt{\left(\frac{r_{\max}}{r}\right)^B \cdot W_{\max}^2 \cdot e^{1-(r_{\max}/r)^B} + \frac{(r \cdot f)^2}{4} - \frac{r \cdot f}{2}}, \quad (1)$$

$$P_A = P_c + (P_n - P_c) \cdot e^{-(r_{\max}/r)^B}, \quad (2)$$

$$B = \frac{\rho_{\text{air}} \cdot W_{\max}^2 \cdot e}{P_n - P_c}, \quad (3)$$

533 where P_c , W_{\max} , and r_{\max} are central pressure, maximum wind speed, and the radius of
 534 maximum winds, as included in the storm track, f is the Coriolis parameter, B is Holland's
 535 fitting parameter¹⁰⁹, $P_n = 1013$ hPa is ambient pressure, and e is Euler's number. As storm

536 track input we use observational data from IBTrACS, the most comprehensive global dataset
 537 of historical tropical cyclone activity⁸⁷. IBTrACS collects information reported by the WMO
 538 Regional Specialised Meteorological Centers (RSMCs) and by agencies in Shanghai and Hong
 539 Kong. For each of the 71 TC events in our study, we extract the IBTrACS data about the
 540 following variables, following the methodology in ISIMIP3a¹¹⁰: time, location of the storm
 541 centre, central pressure, maximum 1-minute sustained wind speed, environmental pressure,
 542 radius of maximum wind speeds, and radius of the outermost closed isobar. Apart from the
 543 parametric wind and pressure fields, no meteorological forcing is applied in our setup.

544 The interaction of the water flow with the air above and the surface below are imple-
 545 mented as friction terms in the momentum equations of the SWEs: For wind friction, the
 546 Garratt wind drag law¹¹¹, an approximation of the Charnock equation¹¹², is used:

$$C_w = \min(2 \cdot 10^{-3}, (0.75 + 0.067 \cdot W) \cdot 10^{-3}). \quad (4)$$

547 The bottom friction is implemented as a Manning term:

$$C_f = \frac{g \cdot n^2}{h^{4/3}}, \quad (5)$$

548 where g is the gravitational constant, and n is the ‘‘Manning coefficient’’, which is set to 0.050
 549 on land, and 0.025 off shore.

550 As output, maximum inundation heights in coastal areas are stored on a 30 arc-second
 551 grid (in meters above ground, and above geoid). For this purpose, the internal height values,
 552 which are a primary variable in the SWEs, are interpolated from the internal mesh of varying
 553 resolution to the regular 30 arc-second grid. In addition to the inundation maps, we configure
 554 GeoClaw to store time series of flood heights at predefined output locations, according to the
 555 GESLA3 tide gauges and CoDEC-ERA5 output locations (see below). The surge dynamics
 556 are stored at the (varying) temporal resolution of the GeoClaw simulation run, but are
 557 resampled by taking hourly averages for the evaluation. This agrees with the resolution of
 558 GESLA3 tide gauge measurements (see below).

559 For our analysis, we ran GeoClaw on nodes of a high-performance cluster with 64 GB of
 560 RAM and 16 cores at 3.4 GHz each (i.e., 16 OpenMP threads). The run times (wall times)
 561 for a single TC event ranged from 30 seconds to 21 hours with an average run time of 2 hours

562 and 34 minutes. Half of the TC events were completed in under one hour, and only 23% of
563 the TC events needed more than 3 hours. Note that the run times differ a lot between TC
564 events because GeoClaw uses adaptive mesh refinement so that the computational demand
565 depends strongly on the intensity of an event. Many events in our analysis are Category 1 or
566 weaker (Fig. 2). For comparison, a two-step modeling framework based on LISFLOOD-FP
567 at 90 m resolution has been reported to require 24 hours when running on 200 cores¹¹³. Note
568 that there is a GPU implementation of GeoClaw¹¹⁴ that was not used in this study, but
569 would further speed up the process for operational applications (3.6 to 6.4 times faster than
570 a 16-core CPU).

571 GTSM dynamic ocean model

572 We use pre-computed outputs of the Global Tide and Surge Model (GTSM) from the ex-
573 treme sea level dataset CoDEC-ERA5⁷⁰ that is freely available from [https://zenodo.org/](https://zenodo.org/records/8322750)
574 [records/8322750](https://zenodo.org/records/8322750)¹¹⁵. The data comes as hourly-resolved sea level time series at 18,719 out-
575 put locations, equidistantly located every 50 km along the smoothed global coastlines. We
576 refer to the literature for a detailed description of the model setup⁷⁰. Here, we provide a
577 summary for the convenience of the reader.

578 The Global Tide and Surge Model (GTSM)⁷⁰ uses the Delft3D Flexible Mesh software
579 to solve the depth-averaged shallow water equations (SWEs) on a global unstructured mesh
580 with spatially varying grid resolution which varies between 25 km in the deep ocean and
581 2.5 km in coastal areas. Only ocean and no land grid cells are part of the model grid so that
582 coastal inundation processes are not modeled. At the coastal boundary, the movement of
583 particles tangential to the coastline is assumed to be shearless (free-slip boundary condition).
584 Astronomical tidal forcing is applied in the form of tide generating forces in the momentum
585 equation of the SWEs¹¹⁶. The model is forced with wind and pressure fields from the
586 European Reanalysis (ERA5)¹¹⁷.

587 CLIMADA static inundation model

588 We apply the static inundation model included in the open-source risk analysis tool box
589 CLIMADA⁵⁸ to the historical events considered in this study. A detailed description of the
590 model can be found in the official documentation (<https://climada-petals.readthedocs>.

591 [io/en/latest/tutorial/climada_hazard_TCSurgeBathtub.html](https://www.climada.org/en/latest/tutorial/climada_hazard_TCSurgeBathtub.html)). Separately in each grid
592 cell, this model estimates inundation heights using a linear relationship with three physi-
593 cal predictors: wind speed, distance to coast, and topographical elevation. While the model
594 lacks statistical and physical justification and has not been validated with observational data
595 so far, it is still used for probabilistic impact and risk assessments due to its computational
596 simplicity as well as low requirements on data availability⁵⁹.

597 Compared to other static inundation models, the CLIMADA model does not require max-
598 imum surge heights as an input but it implicitly estimates surge heights from maximum wind
599 speeds. The wind speeds are derived from IBTrACS⁸⁷ storm track data sets using a paramet-
600 ric model that is implemented as part of CLIMADA^{109,118}. For storm track and topographical
601 elevation, we use the same data used in our GeoClaw setup (see above). The only other in-
602 put data set is the gridded Distance to the Nearest Coast dataset that is freely distributed
603 by NASA (<https://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov/resources/docs/distfromcoast/>). We
604 configure CLIMADA to compute outputs on the same rectangular grid with 1 km resolution
605 that is used in our GeoClaw setup.

606 **Aqueduct static inundation model**

607 We apply the static, bathtub-type inundation model that is published as part of the World
608 Resources Institute’s Aqueduct project³⁷, and available as open-source software from <https://github.com/Deltares/aqueduct-coastal-flooding/tree/py38>
609 under the terms of the GNU General Public License version 3. This model derives inundation heights in inland
610 coastal areas from maximum surge heights given at points along the coastline. Even though
611 the model is static, it implements a concept of friction which is called “resistance factor”⁷¹,
612 meaning that flood heights decrease with the distance to coast, depending on surface prop-
613 erties. The resistance factor is 0.5 m km^{-1} on open terrain, with higher values for higher
614 topographical elevation. For grid cells that are frequently inundated by permanent water
615 bodies, the resistance factor is reduced proportional to water occurrence statistics, so that
616 the resistance factor vanishes in grid cells that are permanently part of water bodies. For
617 water occurrence statistics, we use the Copernicus Global Surface Water raster data for 1984-
618 2019 at 30 m (0.9 arc-seconds) resolution¹¹⁹. For each grid cell, the surface water occurrence,
619 i.e. the frequency with which water was present in the study period as a percentage between
620

621 0 and 100, is provided.

622 Previous studies used the Aqueduct model to derive inundated areas from coastal peak
623 storm tide outputs of the Global Tide and Surge Model (GTSM)^{25,37,71,72}. Its performance
624 has not been validated with observational data so far. We apply the Aqueduct model to peak
625 storm tides at the CoDEC-ERA5 output locations computed with GTSM and GeoClaw (see
626 above).

627 Performance indicators

628 For the evaluation of the simulation results, we compare the areas marked as flooded by
629 either one of the satellite-based or modelled flood extents using several performance metrics.
630 Since the prediction of flood extents is a binary classification problem (with classes “wet” for
631 positive and “dry” for negative), the scores are expressed in terms of areas classified as true
632 positive (n_{11}), true negative (n_{00}), false positive (n_{01}) and false negative (n_{10})⁷⁵.

633 The Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC)^{120,121}, also known as (Yule) Phi coefficient,
634 is the Pearson correlation coefficient estimated for two binary variables:

$$\text{MCC} = \frac{n_{11} \cdot n_{00} - n_{01} \cdot n_{10}}{\sqrt{(n_{11} + n_{01}) \cdot (n_{11} + n_{10}) \cdot (n_{00} + n_{01}) \cdot (n_{00} + n_{10})}}. \quad (6)$$

635 The F1 score⁷⁶ is the harmonic mean of *precision* (positive predictive value, PPV) and *recall*
636 (hit rate, HR):

$$\text{F1} = \frac{2 \cdot \text{HR} \cdot \text{PPV}}{\text{HR} + \text{PPV}}, \quad (7)$$

$$\text{HR} = \frac{n_{11}}{n_{11} + n_{10}}, \quad (8)$$

$$\text{PPV} = \frac{n_{11}}{n_{11} + n_{01}}. \quad (9)$$

637 Note that we set the F1 score to the value 0 if $n_{11} = 0$. The F2 score⁷⁷, also known as critical
638 success index (CSI), threat score (TS), flood area index (FAI), or Jaccard index, is the ratio
639 of the area classified as wet by both (model and observation) divided by the area classified
640 as wet by any of the two:

$$\text{F2} = \frac{n_{11}}{n_{10} + n_{11} + n_{01}}. \quad (10)$$

641 The TNR score (ratio of true negative areas), also known as specificity, is the ratio of areas

642 marked as dry by both divided by the areas marked as dry in the observation:

$$\text{TNR} = \frac{n_{00}}{n_{00} + n_{01}}. \quad (11)$$

643 In this study, the bias score¹²² is defined as the log-fraction between wet areas, predictions
644 compared to observations:

$$\text{Bias} = \log\left(\frac{n_{11} + n_{01}}{n_{11} + n_{10}}\right). \quad (12)$$

645 Note that the Bias score can take the value $-\infty$ in cases where the model does not predict
646 any flooding. However, this does not affect the aggregation of map-by-map scores since we
647 do not take averages but only quantiles which are robust for this kind of outlier.

648 MCC, F1 and F2 quantify the overall quality of the prediction with a single number that
649 takes into account true and false positive and negative classifications. While the MCC score
650 has a minimum value of -1, F1 and F2 range from 0 to 1. For all three scores, a higher value
651 is better, with a value of 1 denoting an exact fit. The TNR score takes a value of 100%
652 in case of a perfect fit, but contrary to the previous scores, a higher TNR does not imply
653 that the fit quality is better, in general. A low TNR indicates that a prediction tends to
654 overpredict, but underprediction is not penalized: classifying all cells as dry yields a perfect
655 TNR of 100%.

656 Data on satellite-based flood extents

657 The main source of validation data for our study are satellite-based flood extents. We
658 consider data from three flood extent data bases:

- 659 1. In the Global Flood Database (GFD), flood extents have been derived from MODIS
660 satellite measurements¹²³. Each of the 913 flood extents is linked to an entry in the
661 flood list of the Dartmouth Flood Observatory (DFO)¹²⁴, covering the period 2000
662 to 2018. Using the description, geolocation and date of the entries, we matched TC
663 events from IBTrACS to 61 of the available flood extents. We removed 6 events from
664 the selection since we found no overlap in coastal areas between the storm geometry
665 according to IBTrACS and the flood extents provided by GFD.
- 666 2. There is a continuously updated collection of rapid response flood maps published
667 directly by DFO¹²⁴, based on MODIS satellite measurements. The collection is not

668 provided in machine readable form, but only for human access through a web interface,
669 as RGB color images, most of them not properly georeferenced. Among those, we
670 identified 61 maps that are related to 44 TC events in IBTrACS, covering the period
671 2001 to 2019. We manually converted these maps to a machine-readable georeferenced
672 format for further analysis. After that, 15 maps were removed from the selection
673 due to a missing overlap with IBTrACS storm geometries. In previous studies, DFO
674 flood extents were used for a selection of inland flood events in Nigeria (2012)¹²⁵,
675 Mozambique (2007)¹²⁶, and for flood events along the Brahmaputra river (2012)¹²⁷.
676 Other than that, the DFO flood extents have not been used for similar flood extent
677 validation studies.

678 3. Finally, the near real time (NRT) system for inundation maps named RAdar-Produced
679 Inundation Diary (RAPID) is based on synthetic aperture radar (SAR) devices on-
680 board earth-orbiting platforms¹²⁸. A selection of maps produced with RAPID is pub-
681 licly available in machine-readable form. Among those, we identified 9 flood maps that
682 were related to 6 TC events in IBTrACS, covering the years 2016 to 2019, all located
683 in the North Atlantic region. One of the maps was removed from the selection as
684 covering only non-coastal areas. Due to the SAR-based measurements, the flood maps
685 only cover parts of the affected areas.

686 Altogether, we selected 97 flood maps that are related to 71 TC events in IBTrACS,
687 covering the years 2000 to 2019. For the comparison of the simulated flood extents with
688 observational data (Fig. 5), we aggregated the satellite-based flood extents from their orig-
689 inal resolution (between 1 and 27 arc-seconds, 20–850 m) to the resolution of all simulation
690 outputs (30 arc-seconds, 900 m). During aggregation, a grid cell is classified as flooded if at
691 least one of the underlying grid cells in the original resolution was flooded. We only include
692 grid cells with a height of between 0 and 10 meters above geoid, and outside of permanent
693 water bodies. A threshold of 10 m is common to define the low-elevation coastal zone in
694 impact assessments⁵⁶. To define permanent water bodies, we use the Copernicus Global
695 Surface Water raster data for 1984-2019 at 30 m (0.9 arc-seconds) resolution¹¹⁹. For each
696 grid cell, the surface water occurrence, i.e. the frequency with which water was present in
697 the study period as a percentage between 0 and 100, is provided. For our analysis, we aggre-
698 gate the raster data to the resolution of the model outputs (30 arc-seconds) using averaging

699 and include only grid cells for which the occurrence frequency exceeds 5%.

700 The size of the flood maps and the size of the wet and dry areas within each map varies
701 a lot from map to map. The size of the coastal area (including both wet and dry) covered by
702 the 97 satellite-based flood maps differs by orders of magnitude from map to map, ranging
703 from 170 to more than 75,000 km² (Fig. 6a). In total, 200,000 km² are classified as wet. For
704 each map, this is between 0 and more than 27,000 km², with a mean and median wet area of
705 2,060 and 480 km² (66% interval: 100–3,400 km²). 75 extents have smaller than average wet
706 areas. Together, 8 extents account for more than 50% of the areas observed as wet. For 17
707 among the 97 flood maps, the wet area is less than 0.05% (100 km²) of the total wet area.
708 Note that restricting our evaluation to extents with a medium-size observed area of between
709 100 and 1000 km² does not change the results of our analysis significantly (Figs. S1a to S1e)

710 For our analysis, we process the simulation outputs of the four approaches, a grid cell is
711 marked as flooded if the flood depth exceeds 10 cm. This threshold is appropriate for the low
712 resolution outputs that we consider here. In studies with high-resolution LiDAR elevation
713 data, a lower threshold is also common, e.g. 1 cm¹²⁹. Note that omitting the threshold does
714 not change the results of our analysis significantly (Figs. S1f to S1j).

715 Data from tide gauge measurements

716 We use the hourly tide gauge data provided by GESLA version 3 (GESLA3)⁸⁶, a consis-
717 tent global data set of tide gauge measurements. There are duplicate tide gauge stations in
718 GESLA3, e.g. most stations operated by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Adminis-
719 tration (NOAA) are also listed in the database by the University of Hawaii Sea Level Center
720 (UHSLC). Since GESLA3 collects data from both providers, several stations are listed twice
721 in GESLA3. Therefore, we selected for each flood map and tide gauge location the tide gauge
722 provider in GESLA3 with the lowest number of missing values. Furthermore, we restrict to
723 the stations within the geographical area of each flood extent that were operational during
724 the time of landfall of the storms. Since the flood extents are often larger than the actual
725 extent of the TC, we restricted the analysis to the tide gauge locations that lie within the
726 IBTrACS storm geometries. We further excluded tide gauge stations with large reporting
727 gaps in the period of the TC event. More precisely, at most 1 hourly data point may be
728 missing in each 24 hour-period.

729 Using the satellite altimetry (see above), we shifted the water levels in the tide gauge
730 records so that they are relative to the geoid. For that, we extract the annual means from the
731 gridded satellite altimetry product at the location of each tide gauge station. Note however,
732 that this correction is subject to major uncertainty, since the satellite altimetry product has
733 a resolution of only 0.25 degrees (approximately 25 km). Furthermore, the satellite altimetry
734 can only provide height information for grid cells that are off shore. Many tide gauge stations
735 lie very close to the coast or even in narrow estuaries, so that their location is often in grid
736 cells that are not off shore according to the satellite altimetry. In those cases, we consider the
737 average value of neighboring grid cells. We excluded stations from the analysis where neither
738 the containing nor any of the directly neighboring grid cells has altimetry information.

739 After that, there remained 383 records from 213 distinct tide gauge stations, covering
740 34 of the 71 storm events. Only the time span where a TC-signal is to be expected in the
741 surge was used in the evaluation. For that, we estimated an hourly wind speed time series
742 at each tide location using the wind field model included in CLIMADA (see above). The
743 time span for the analysis was then chosen to start 12 hours before the first time the wind
744 speed exceeded tropical storm strength (17.5 m/s), and end 12 hours after the last time the
745 wind speed was above that threshold.

746 **Data from field measurements (high water marks)**

747 For a set of 11 of the 71 events in our analysis, high-water marks (HWMs) from the USGS
748 Flood Event Viewer⁸⁵ are available. This product is only available for the USA. It consists of
749 field measurements by volunteers and trained USGS hydrographers, usually directly following
750 a flood event¹³⁰. The observers take note of mud, seed, debris, cut or wash lines on the inside
751 and outside of buildings (in residential areas) and on open terrain features such as trees,
752 shrubs, grasses, bluffs or river banks. Most HWMs are documented with a photography, a
753 numerical value indicating the height above ground in feet, and the vertical uncertainty in
754 one of six categories of uncertainty ranging from Excellent (± 0.05 ft) to Very Poor (more
755 than ± 0.40 ft).

756 In previous studies, the HWMs have been used for the validation of a rapid storm surge
757 forecasting framework¹³¹, and for the validation and comparison of event-based flood inun-
758 dation mapping services¹³². In general, field measurements such as the HWMs used here

759 are commonly taken as a complement to conventional water-level records in assessing model
760 performance¹³³.

761 HWMs are only available for the conterminous United States and only for selected TCs.
762 Since the horizontal and vertical datums vary among HWMs, we excluded HWMs with
763 missing datum information. We reprojected the remaining HWMs to the EGM 96 vertical
764 datum, the geoid model used in the global DEM datasets (see above). For 11 of the 71 storm
765 events for which flood extents are available, we identify 2171 HWMs that lie on land within
766 the IBTrACS storm geometries and at a topographic height of at most 10 meters (according
767 to our DEM data set). For our main HWM analysis (Fig. 9), we only use the 1007 HWM
768 locations that are classified as coastal (for the same analysis with only riverine locations, see
769 [Supplementary Fig. S4](#)).

770 **Limitations of the performance indicators**

771 Since we have GTSM hydrographs on a fixed set of output locations, we could not compare
772 the simulated GTSM hydrographs with observed hydrographs at the exact locations of the
773 GESLA3 tide gauge stations. Following previous studies^{70,115}, we compared each GESLA3
774 hydrograph to the simulated GTSM hydrograph at the closest available output location.
775 However, we found several examples where the tide gauge stations and output locations
776 were separated by estuaries or small islands. In those cases, the difference in the hydrographs
777 might be dominated by the difference in location. Therefore, we excluded those tide gauge
778 stations from the analysis, where the distance to the next GTSM output location is larger
779 than 10 km. The specific choice of 10 km was a trade-off between the number of tide gauge
780 stations we remove and the error due to the distance between GTSM grid cell and tide gauge
781 station. In the literature, The mean difference between modeled GTSM and observed water
782 levels is reported to be 0.19 m for the 1 in 10 year peaks⁷⁰. This agrees well with the analysis
783 of TC hydrographs in this study: We find that the mean difference between modeled GTSM
784 and observed GESLA3 peak water levels is 0.26 m across the 71 TC events. To complement
785 the aggregate statistics in [Fig. 10a](#), we also illustrate the comparison of maximum water
786 levels using a scatter plot in [Supplementary Fig. S5](#).

787 In the comparison of HWMs, we evaluate the absolute inundation heights (above geoid)
788 instead of the inundation heights above ground because the inundation heights above ground

789 are missing for 45% of the coastal HWM locations, across all 11 US storms for which HWMs
790 are available. Further, we do not consider the locations that were classified as dry by the
791 model in the aggregate statistics (Fig. 9a). This means that a different set and number
792 of HWM locations goes into the evaluation for each of the models, ranging from $N = 217$
793 (GTSM+Aqueduct) to $N = 288$ (GeoClaw) (Fig. 9b). We found that the results do not
794 change significantly when the inundation heights above ground are compared (Figs. S3b
795 to S3d), or when including locations modeled as dry (Figs. S3a and S3c). Finally, we also
796 applied the comparison after restricting to HWMs for which the deviation of the DEM to
797 the recorded elevation does not exceed half the recorded inundation height (Fig. S3d; this
798 excludes 90% of the HWMs from the comparison).

799 We report five different performance scores for the evaluation of flood extents, three
800 of which are overall measures of performance (Figs. 5a to 5c). In flood extent validation
801 studies, F1 and F2 are the predominant indicators of model performance, even though they
802 are known to be biased in favor of overpredictions⁷⁸. MCC is generally regarded as a more
803 informative and true score if the class sizes vary⁷⁹. Also, contrary to MCC, F1 and F2 are
804 not symmetric, i.e., they will change when exchanging the meanings of “wet” and “dry”. We
805 decided to complement the three overall scores by TNR and bias because they represent
806 aspects of the classification problem that are least reflected in F1 and F2, and bias is only
807 implicitly included in MCC.

808 The performance scores of all models considered in this study appear to be quite low and
809 need to be interpreted in context. They cannot easily be compared to regional analyses or to
810 studies about freshwater or compound flooding. For example, all four approaches considered
811 in this study have average F2 scores of less than 25%, while F2 scores of less than 30% are
812 very uncommon in the literature^{84,134} (typical values are between 30% and 50%^{129,135}, even
813 exceeding 80% in some cases^{136,137}). In assessments of approaches that model freshwater
814 flooding over land, it is much easier to restrict to a model area that clearly excludes flooding
815 from surge, e.g. for Hurricane Harvey⁸⁴. In contrast, our study is about approaches that
816 model TC-related flooding from storm surge, isolated from freshwater flooding and compound
817 effects. For validation purposes, it would be desirable to have observational flood extents
818 that are purely caused by storm surge. However, in the TC context, storm surge is always
819 accompanied by heavy rainfall so that none of the observational flood extents can clearly be
820 attributed to surge alone. When comparing the surge model outputs with the compound

821 flood extents, low performance scores are to be expected. There is another aspect that
822 influences the scores seen in studies about freshwater flooding: It is comparably easy for
823 a flood model to correctly classify the permanent water bodies (rivers, lakes) as wet. Still,
824 studies about freshwater flooding usually do not exclude the permanent water bodies from the
825 scoring^{126,135}. In our study, it is comparably easy for a surge model to correctly classify the
826 ocean as wet. However, we do not include permanent water bodies in the calculation of the
827 performance scores, since otherwise, the size of the ocean area included in the rectangular
828 flood map would dominate the results. If a flood map containing a larger portion of the
829 ocean scored automatically better than a flood map that only contains a small ocean strip,
830 summarizing scores over a global set of flood maps would be difficult. So far, our study is the
831 first to evaluate a pure TC storm surge modeling approach using a global set of observational
832 flood extents. Therefore, we do not find comparable score values in the literature.

833 The total scores of GeoClaw are much better than the map-by-map scores. However,
834 the qualitative differences between the models remain mostly unchanged (Fig. 5). Similarly,
835 the qualitative statements are robust to the exclusion of very small and very large (e.g.,
836 less than 100 km² or more than 1000 km²) flood extents from the analysis, when removing
837 the minimum flood threshold of 10 cm, or when considering the flood maps from each data
838 source separately (Supplementary Fig. S1).

839 **Limitations in the considered drivers of flooding**

840 The GTSM data we use is only driven by meteorological forcing from ERA5, while GeoClaw
841 is forced by parametric TC wind fields. Forcing ocean models with ERA5 data is known
842 to underestimate TC-induced surge heights, and the forcing can be improved by overlaying
843 parametric TC wind fields^{13,25,90,91}. On the other hand, the choice of parametric wind field is
844 important in TC storm surge modeling¹³⁸, and post-processing methods have been proposed
845 to improve the outputs of parametric models¹³⁹.

846 Coastal flood protection is not included in this analysis, and many exposed regions are
847 protected by dikes and storm surge barriers up to a certain design standard. Many cities
848 have a protection standard that equals a 100-year return period¹⁴⁰, and will be protected
849 against many storms considered in this study. This might be one reason why the tendency
850 of GeoClaw to underestimate hydrographs (Fig. 10a) does not translate to the bias in the

851 flood extent evaluation (Fig. 5e).

852 In addition to the inclusion of flow dynamics, the different assumptions on friction might
853 explain some of the differences between the dynamic model GeoClaw and the static model
854 Aqueduct (Geoclaw+Aqueduct). Both implement a concept of bottom friction over land.
855 While the “resistance factor” in Aqueduct is conceptually different from the Manning for-
856 mulation in GeoClaw, both concepts come with a calibration parameter expressing terrain
857 roughness that can have an important impact on overland flow¹⁴¹.

858 Note that, while GeoClaw has been used for TC storm surge modeling before^{69,142}, the
859 main application of GeoClaw is tsunami modeling where it is popular in probabilistic ap-
860 plications with large ensembles of inundation scenarios⁹³. Since TC analyses are also often
861 based on probabilistic ensembles of events^{88,143,144}, this would be an interesting future appli-
862 cation of our approach. As an alternative, the one-step approach could in principle also be
863 implemented with more advanced ocean models like ADCIRC, GTSM or SCHISM that are
864 able to account for more complex environmental forcing than GeoClaw⁵⁰.

865 Data Availability

866 All data needed to reproduce the findings reported in this article are openly accessible. A
867 detailed description of the exact versions of the datasets used, including instructions how
868 to download and preprocess these, are provided in the “README.md” file of the archive
869 “evaluation.zip” in the project’s zenodo repository [https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.](https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10419306)
870 [10419306](https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10419306). Further, machine-readable source data for all figures, supplementary figures, and
871 supplementary tables are provided with this paper as Supplementary Data file.

872 Code Availability

873 All code that was used i) for the GeoClaw setup, ii) for the static inundation models, iii) for
874 the preprocessing of validation data sources, and iv) to analyze the data and produce the
875 figures was implemented in Python 3.9 (<https://www.python.org/>) with CLIMADA 3.3.3
876 (<https://zenodo.org/record/7691855>), and is openly available from [https://dx.doi.](https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10419306)
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1308 **Authors contributions**

1309 T.V., C.O., and K.F. designed the analysis. T.V. implemented the inundation models and
1310 calculated the flood depth maps with the support of S.T. T.V. further conducted the sta-
1311 tistical analysis, and generated all plots and tables. All authors contributed to the analysis.
1312 T.V., C.O., and M.M. wrote the manuscript with contributions from all authors. All authors
1313 discussed the results.

1314 **Competing Interests**

1315 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

1316

Supplementary Information (SI)

1317

Modeling surge dynamics improves coastal flood estimates in a
1318 global set of tropical cyclones

1319

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1322 Supplementary Notes

1323 **Supplementary Note S1: Further evaluation of limitations of satellite-** 1324 **based flood extents**

1325 The main observational reference data sets for our analysis are satellite-based flood extents
1326 which do not allow to differentiate between fluvial, pluvial, and surge-induced flooding. We
1327 reduced the inland flood signal in the reference data by restricting our analysis to areas below
1328 10 m elevation. Further, the satellite-based flood extents likely underestimate flooded areas
1329 (see Results). In this section, we present additional evaluations that have been conducted
1330 to confirm and better understand the limitations of satellite-based flood extents.

1331 To demonstrate the large uncertainties of satellite-based flood extents, we compared the
1332 flood extents to field measurements and found that more than 27% of the HWM locations
1333 were not marked as flooded in the satellite flood maps. Further, the disagreement between
1334 observational products (and thus uncertainty) is very large, as indicated by a comparison of
1335 flood extents of the same storm event from different satellite-based products (**Supplemen-**
1336 **tary Fig. S2**). For 23 of the 71 storms we have flood maps from more than one database, and
1337 some of the areas covered by the flood maps have overlapping areas. There are 20 flood maps
1338 from DFO that overlap with reports from GFD. While the agreement across flood maps is
1339 much better than the agreement between models and flood maps, the MCC score (ranging
1340 from -1 to 1) is still quite low, with a median MCC value of 0.34 (**Fig. S2a**). GeoClaw has a
1341 median MCC value of 0.10 within the overlapping areas. With total instead of map-by-map
1342 scoring, the value is 0.38 (GeoClaw: 0.29). All 5 flood maps by RAPID that are included
1343 in this study have an overlap with DFO, and the median MCC score of the overlap is 0.16
1344 (total score 0.58, **Fig. S2f**). Only 2 flood maps overlap between GFD and RAPID, with a
1345 median and total MCC score of 0.10 and 0.26 (**Fig. S2k**).

1346 To demonstrate that our truncation of flood extents removed a large part of fluvial and
1347 pluvial flooding in the satellite-based flood extents, we additionally compared the observa-
1348 tions to outputs of the global flood model (GFM) CaMa-Flood as provided by ISIMIP3a^{43,110}.
1349 CaMa-Flood translates runoff estimates from a hydrological model into gridded maps of
1350 annual maximum inundation heights at 60 arc-seconds resolution, accounting for current
1351 flood protection standards at the sub-national scale from the FLOPROS database¹⁴⁵. We use

1352 runoff simulations from 8 global hydrological models (GHMs): CLASSIC, CWatM, H08, Hy-
1353 droPy, JULES-W2, MIROC-INTEG-LAND, ORCHIDEE-MICT, and WEB-DHM-SG. The
1354 hydrological models are forced by precipitation from W5E5¹⁴⁶, which is also included with
1355 ISIMIP3a. W5E5 combines WFDE5 v2.0 (WATCH Forcing Data methodology applied to
1356 ERA5 reanalysis data over land;¹⁴⁷) with data from the latest version of ERA5 over the
1357 ocean. For our comparison, we take the median flood depth in each grid cell across the eight
1358 hydrological models. The resulting flood depth estimates are then reprojected to the extent
1359 and resolution of the satellite-based flood extents using bilinear interpolation.

1360 When adding the flood extents from CaMa-Flood to the GeoClaw results, the perfor-
1361 mance scores for the evaluation of satellite observations improve only slightly. Further,
1362 CaMa-Flood alone scores lower than all of the surge inundation models considered in this
1363 study. The TNR of the combined model output is exceptionally low (84%) and the combi-
1364 nation shows a clear tendency to overpredict (positive bias, +0.55). This confirms that in
1365 our selection of flood maps, storm surge is the primary driver of inundation (Figs. S6b to S6f
1366 and Supplementary Tbl. S6).

1367 When considering coastal HWM locations, CaMa-Flood classified less than 1% of the
1368 HWMs as wet (not shown). When only considering riverine HWM locations, CaMa-Flood
1369 correctly classifies 31% of the locations as wet, and GeoClaw only 16%. The two models
1370 complement each other for the riverine HWMs as both models taken together correctly
1371 classify 44% of HWMs as wet (Figs. S6g and S6h and Supplementary Tbl. S6).

1372 Note that summing up the impacts of coastal and fluvial flooding (as we do for this
1373 analysis) is known to lead to large errors, especially in coastal watersheds¹⁴⁸. For example,
1374 these compound effects have played a crucial role in the case of Harvey^{3,4}.

1375 **Supplementary Figures S1–S9**

Supplementary Fig. S1. Performance scores for subsets of the satellite-based flood extent data. The colored boxes denote interquartile ranges of map-by-map scores, with a black horizontal line for the median value, whiskers for the 95% intervals, and circles for the minimum and maximum values. Black stars denote the total score. For a detailed description of the panels in each row, see Fig. 5.

Supplementary Fig. S2. Comparison of satellite-observations from different sources. For the areas, where the flood maps from different observational sources (DFO, GFD, and RAPID) overlap, the performance scores among the observations are shown for each combination of observational sources: GFD (a–e) and RAPID (f–j) compared to DFO, and RAPID compared to GFD (k–o). The performance scores of the modeled flood extents is shown for reference. The colored boxes denote interquartile ranges of map-by-map scores, with a black horizontal line for the median value, whiskers for the 95% intervals, and circles for the minimum and maximum values. Black stars denote the total score. For a detailed description of the panels in each row, see Fig. 5.

Supplementary Fig. S3. Alternative ways of comparing with high water marks (HWMs). In Fig. 9a, simulated and observed inundation heights above geoid are compared, and locations are excluded from the comparison if the location is classified as dry (no flooding) according to the model. Alternatively, the inundation heights above ground can be compared (b, c, and d), but note that this information is missing for 45% of the coastal HWM locations. Further, locations classified as dry can be included in the comparison (a, c, and d). Finally, locations can be excluded where the deviation of the DEM to the recorded elevation is larger than half the inundation height recorded at the location (d). Note that this excludes almost 95% of the HWMs from the comparison. The colored boxes denote interquartile ranges, with a black horizontal line for the median value, whiskers for 95% intervals, and circles for the minimum and maximum values. For a detailed description of the panels, see Fig. 9.

Supplementary Fig. S4. Comparison with riverine high water marks (HWMs). The analysis from Fig. 9 (a, b) and Supplementary Fig. S3 (c-f), but for riverine instead of coastal HWMs. Note that height above ground information is missing for 27% of the riverine HWM locations, and 88% of the riverine HWMs are excluded in panel f, because the deviation of the DEM to the recorded elevation is larger than half the inundation height recorded at the location. The colored boxes denote 66% intervals with a black line for the median value. For a detailed description of the panels, see Fig. 9.

Supplementary Fig. S5. Scatter plots for the observed and simulated maximum water levels. **a** Maximum water levels simulated by GeoClaw (y-axis) are compared to observations in GESLA3 (x-axis). **b** Maximum water levels simulated by GTSM (y-axis) are compared to observations in GESLA3 (x-axis). **c** Maximum water levels simulated by GeoClaw (y-axis) are compared to simulations by GTSM (x-axis). For summary statistics, see [Fig. 10a](#).

Supplementary Fig. S6. Model agreement for the inland flood model CaMa-Flood. **a** An exemplary flood extent output of CaMa-Flood for Hurricane Harvey (cf. Fig. 3). **b** An exemplary flood extent output of CaMa-Flood for Hurricane Rita (cf. Fig. 4). **c–g** Performance scores for the evaluation of satellite-based flood extents. The colored boxes denote interquartile ranges of map-by-map scores, with a black horizontal line for the median value, whiskers for the 95% intervals, and circles for the minimum and maximum values. The black stars denote the total scores. For a detailed description of the panels, see Fig. 5. **h–i** Performance scores for the evaluation of riverine high water marks. The colored boxes denote interquartile ranges, with a black line for the median value, whiskers for the 95% intervals, and circles for the minimum and maximum values. For a detailed description of the panels, see Fig. 9.

Supplementary Fig. S7. Flood extent performance scores by astronomical tide assumption. The performance scores of modeled flood extents are shown for each of three assumptions on astronomical tides in the GeoClaw model setup: minimum (**a–e**), mean (**f–j**), and maximum (**k–o**, main specification) astronomical tides. For a detailed description of the panels, see [Fig. 5](#).

Supplementary Fig. S8. Comparison with high water marks (HWMs) by astronomical tide assumption. Model outputs are compared to HWMs for each of three assumptions on astronomical tides in the GeoClaw model setup: minimum (a–b), mean (c–d), and maximum (e–f, main specification) astronomical tides. For a detailed description of the panels, see Fig. 9.

1376 **Supplementary Tables S1–S7**

Supplementary Tbl. S1. Additional information about storms covered by this analysis. The event ID in the IBTrACS⁸⁷ database, the official name and year of the storm, the storm intensity according to the Saffir-Simpson Hurricane Scale (SSH), the dates of the satellite observations, the number of tide gauge stations (GESLA3), the number of GTSM output locations (CoDEC), the number of coastal and riverine high water marks (HWMs), the flooded area according to each of the satellite-based flood extents (if available). This table covers the North Atlantic and eastern North Pacific region. For other regions, see [Supplementary Tbls. S2 and S3](#).

IBTrACS ID	Name (Year)	SSH	Date (MM/DD)	GESLA3	CoDEC	HWMs			Flooded area (km ²)		
						Coastal	Riverine	DFO	GFD	RAPID	
2003249N14329	Isabel (2003)	C3	09/20	4	12	51	0	53	-	-	-
2003262N17254	Marty (2003)	C2	10/01	0	79	0	0	-	159	-	-
2004258N16300	Jeanne (2004)	C3	09/21-10/04	51	189	0	0	1683	6792	-	-
2005236N23285	Katrina (2005)	C4	09/02-09/19	17	73	0	0	4817	1200	-	-
2005261N21290	Rita (2005)	C4	09/26-10/01	9	54	12	0	3200	3461	-	-
2005275N19274	Stan (2005)	C1	10/12-10/16	0	12	0	0	1049	617	-	-
2005289N18282	Wilma (2005)	C5	10/25	39	200	2	2	2048	3330	-	-
2005300N10279	Beta (2005)	C3	11/15	0	4	0	0	844	-	-	-
2006237N13298	Ernesto (2006)	C1	09/02-09/07	6	29	0	0	124	162	-	-
2006240N12265	John (2006)	C3	09/04	0	33	0	0	134	-	-	-
2007244N12303	Felix (2007)	C4	09/06-09/12	0	18	0	0	1658	102	-	-
2007297N18300	Noel (2007)	C1	11/04-11/10	0	94	0	0	36	1305	-	-
2007345N18298	Olga (2007)	TS	12/16-12/17	0	28	0	0	77	246	-	-
2008203N18276	Dolly (2008)	C2	07/29	3	21	0	0	-	593	-	-
2008229N18293	Fay (2008)	C1	08/28	27	68	0	0	-	2604	-	-
2008238N13293	Gustav (2008)	C3	09/02	8	40	0	0	-	32	-	-
2009308N11279	Ida (2009)	TS	11/13	2	8	0	0	-	1	-	-
2010176N16278	Alex (2010)	C3	07/07	0	11	0	0	-	24	-	-
2010267N14285	Matthew (2010)	TS	09/30	0	34	0	0	-	171	-	-
2011233N15301	Irene (2011)	C3	09/01-09/13	58	130	92	45	559	1659	-	-
2011279N10257	Jova (2011)	C1	11/01	1	7	0	0	-	15	-	-
2012234N16315	Isaac (2012)	C1	09/07	24	59	100	0	-	746	-	-
2015270N27291	Joaquin (2015)	C3	10/08	0	37	0	0	-	348	-	-
2016273N13300	Matthew (2016)	C4	10/05-10/25	23	76	313	85	6925	-	2410	-
2017228N14314	Harvey (2017)	C3	09/05-09/08	61	78	236	837	11171	-	7627	-
2017242N16333	Irma (2017)	C5	09/16-09/19	146	525	172	511	26198	7803	9873	-
2017260N12310	Maria (2017)	C5	09/21	3	9	24	71	348	-	-	-
2017277N11279	Nate (2017)	TS	10/06-10/07	0	4	0	0	1372	-	-	-
2018242N13343	Florence (2018)	C3	09/19-10/02	27	74	129	695	3615	1040	3341	-
2018280N18273	Michael (2018)	C5	10/11-10/13	24	80	498	61	460	-	834	-
2018292N14261	Willa (2018)	C2	10/26-10/27	0	17	0	0	1790	520	-	-
2019192N29274	Barry (2019)	TS	07/15	8	0	0	0	18	-	-	-
2019261N28264	Imelda (2019)	TS	09/22	10	0	0	0	815	-	-	-

Supplementary Tbl. S2. Continuation of **Supplementary Tbl. S1** for storms in the northern Indian Ocean and western North Pacific.

IBTrACS ID	Name (Year)	SSHS	Date (MM/DD)	GESLA3	CoDEC	HWMs			Flooded area (km ²)		
						Coastal	Riverine	DFO	GFD	RAPID	
2003196N05150	Imbudo (2003)	C3	07/23-07/26	0	25	0	0	355	13	-	
2004174N14146	Mindulle (2004)	C3	07/13	3	194	0	0	163	469	-	
2004231N09147	Aere (2004)	C3	09/12	4	43	0	0	-	9	-	
2004319N10134	Muifa (2004)	C2	11/24-11/29	0	149	0	0	270	278	-	
2005257N15120	Vicente (2005)	C1	09/22-09/24	0	51	0	0	725	686	-	
2008117N11090	Nargis (2008)	C3	05/05-05/22	0	50	0	0	15541	9379	-	
2008206N22133	Fung-Wong (2008)	C1	07/29	1	40	0	0	-	19	-	
2009270N10148	Parma (2009)	C2	10/17	0	22	0	0	-	238	-	
2010198N15123	Chanthu (2010)	C2	07/23	0	28	0	0	-	14	-	
2011266N13139	Nesat (2011)	C2	10/10	0	47	0	0	-	18	-	
2011270N18139	Nalgae (2011)	C4	10/02	1	26	0	0	-	138	-	
2011346N03156	Washi (2011)	C1	12/22	0	61	0	0	-	255	-	
2012301N11087	Nilam (2012)	C1	11/08	0	10	0	0	-	304	-	
2012331N03157	Bopha (2012)	C4	12/04	0	44	0	0	-	62	-	
2014260N13135	Fung-Wong (2014)	C1	10/11	0	7	0	0	-	71	-	
2014362N07130	Jangmi (2015)	TS	01/01	0	22	0	0	-	41	-	
2015207N22091	Komen (2015)	TS	08/19	1	15	0	0	-	183	-	
2015285N14151	Koppu (2015)	C4	10/28	2	64	0	0	-	437	-	
2015344N07145	Melor (2016)	C4	01/06	1	11	0	0	-	725	-	
2017232N19130	Hato (2017)	C2	08/26	1	17	0	0	-	13	-	
2017253N14130	Doksuri (2017)	C3	09/16	0	20	0	0	2579	-	-	
2018195N19138	Son-Tinh (2018)	TS	07/23	0	14	0	0	-	13	-	
2018311N07179	Usagi (2018)	C1	11/29	1	11	0	0	-	63	-	
2019116N02090	Fani (2019)	C3	05/07	0	0	0	0	4318	-	-	

Supplementary Tbl. S3. Continuation of **Supplementary Tbl. S1** for storms in the southern hemisphere.

IBTrACS ID	Name (Year)	SSHS	Date (MM/DD)	GESLA3	CoDEC	HWMs			Flooded area (km ²)			
						Coastal	Riverine	DFO	GFD	RAPID		
200032S11116	Leon-Eline (2000)	C4	03/11	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	92	—
2004056S18125	Monty (2004)	C4	03/07-03/09	3	31	0	0	1604	879	—	—	—
2004061S12072	Gaflo (2004)	C5	03/11	0	0	0	0	86	—	—	—	—
2004072S11146	Fay (2004)	C4	04/01-04/03	2	16	0	0	482	1071	—	—	—
2005017S09061	Ernest (2005)	C3	02/02	0	14	0	0	366	—	—	—	—
2011020S13182	Wilma (2011)	C1	01/31	0	12	0	0	—	18	—	—	—
2012010S24049	Dando (2012)	TS	01/29-02/14	0	3	0	0	163	187	—	—	—
2013018S14138	Oswald (2013)	TS	02/01	0	9	0	0	—	811	—	—	—
2015013S18038	Chedza (2015)	C1	02/09	0	0	0	0	—	373	—	—	—
2015047S15152	Marcia (2015)	C4	02/24	4	12	0	0	—	363	—	—	—
2017082S14152	Debbie (2017)	C3	04/08	6	30	0	0	—	321	—	—	—
2018073S12057	Eliakim (2018)	C1	03/23	0	22	0	0	—	295	—	—	—
2019063S18038	Idai (2019)	C3	03/23	0	0	0	0	12639	—	—	—	—
2019112S10053	Kenneth (2019)	C4	04/28	0	0	0	0	114	—	—	—	—

Supplementary Tbl. S4. Performance indicators for the evaluation of flood extents (total scores and medians of map-by-map scores, separated by \star , with interquartile ranges in parentheses, 95%-intervals in brackets, and minima/maxima in braces, Fig. 5).

Model	MCC	F1	F2	TNR (%)	Bias
GeoClaw	+0.22 \star +0.10	0.34 \star 0.15	0.20 \star 0.08	89% \star 93%	-0.22 \star -0.18
	(+0.04 - +0.21)	(0.07 - 0.28)	(0.04 - 0.16)	(87% - 98%)	(-1.51 - +0.72)
	[-0.05 - +0.46]	[0.00 - 0.62]	[0.00 - 0.44]	[46% - 100%]	[-5.57 - +4.16]
	{-0.08 - +0.57}	{0.00 - 0.83}	{0.00 - 0.72}	{35% - 100%}	{-36.04 - +5.26}
GeoClaw+Aqueduct	+0.11 \star +0.04	0.13 \star 0.03	0.07 \star 0.01	98% \star 99%	-1.65 \star -2.77
	(+0.00 - +0.08)	(0.00 - 0.08)	(0.00 - 0.04)	(98% - 100%)	(-5.27 - -0.80)
	[-0.02 - +0.22]	[0.00 - 0.35]	[0.00 - 0.22]	[70% - 100%]	[-36.04 - +1.86]
	{-0.16 - +0.52}	{0.00 - 0.58}	{0.00 - 0.41}	{13% - 100%}	{-36.04 - +3.40}
GTSM+Aqueduct	+0.10 \star +0.06	0.12 \star 0.04	0.06 \star 0.02	98% \star 99%	-1.74 \star -1.95
	(+0.00 - +0.11)	(0.01 - 0.12)	(0.00 - 0.07)	(97% - 100%)	(-3.77 - -0.39)
	[-0.02 - +0.33]	[0.00 - 0.38]	[0.00 - 0.24]	[78% - 100%]	[-36.04 - +1.95]
	{-0.05 - +0.47}	{0.00 - 0.50}	{0.00 - 0.33}	{64% - 100%}	{-36.04 - +2.48}
CLIMADA	+0.09 \star +0.05	0.18 \star 0.05	0.10 \star 0.03	94% \star 97%	-0.86 \star -1.47
	(+0.00 - +0.11)	(0.01 - 0.19)	(0.00 - 0.10)	(95% - 100%)	(-3.24 - +0.12)
	[-0.08 - +0.35]	[0.00 - 0.47]	[0.00 - 0.31]	[81% - 100%]	[-36.04 - +3.36]
	{-0.12 - +0.46}	{0.00 - 0.60}	{0.00 - 0.43}	{57% - 100%}	{-36.04 - +4.41}

Supplementary Tbl. S5. Performance indicators for the evaluation of coastal high water marks (means and medians, separated by \star , with interquartile ranges in parentheses, 95%-intervals in brackets, and minima/maxima in braces, Fig. 9).

Model	N	Hit rate (%)	Elevation / Inundation height	
			Error (m)	Bias (m)
Observed	853	87.8%	–	–
Topography	666	–	2.15 \star 1.80 (0.84 – 2.88) [0.09 – 7.13] {0.00 – 11.23}	-1.44 \star -1.52 (-2.67 – -0.02) [-7.13 – +3.66] {-11.23 – +6.32}
GeoClaw	896	91.7%	1.51 \star 1.16 (0.57 – 2.02) [0.06 – 4.98] {0.00 – 9.28}	-0.49 \star -0.58 (-1.64 – +0.56) [-4.16 – +3.75] {-7.86 – +9.28}
GeoClaw+Aqueduct	772	79.3%	1.80 \star 1.46 (0.69 – 2.42) [0.10 – 5.60] {0.00 – 8.79}	-0.88 \star -0.97 (-2.12 – +0.26) [-4.91 – +3.65] {-8.68 – +8.79}
GTSM+Aqueduct	762	78.4%	1.90 \star 1.49 (0.78 – 2.65) [0.08 – 5.85] {0.01 – 8.67}	-1.07 \star -1.16 (-2.23 – +0.07) [-5.43 – +3.75] {-8.43 – +8.67}
CLIMADA	772	79.0%	1.61 \star 1.15 (0.49 – 2.15) [0.06 – 5.55] {0.00 – 10.78}	-0.76 \star -0.52 (-1.81 – +0.45) [-5.23 – +2.98] {-10.78 – +9.53}

Supplementary Tbl. S6. Performance indicators for the evaluation of hydrographs (means and medians, separated by \star , with interquartile ranges in parentheses, 95%-intervals in brackets, and minima/maxima in braces, Fig. 10).

Model	Reference	Deviation of max. sea levels		Surge dynamics	
		Absolute (m)	Signed (m)	Pearson	RMSE (m)
GeoClaw	GESLA3	0.50 \star 0.42	-0.22 \star -0.27	0.50 \star 0.66	0.24 \star 0.20
		(0.23 – 0.66)	(-0.57 – +0.10)	(0.37 – 0.82)	(0.12 – 0.31)
		[0.03 – 1.55]	[-1.24 – +1.11]	[-0.74 – 0.95]	[0.04 – 0.68]
		{0.00 – 2.35}	{-2.15 – +2.35}	{-0.93 – 0.98}	{0.03 – 1.08}
GTSM	GESLA3	0.32 \star 0.26	-0.21 \star -0.21	0.65 \star 0.82	0.19 \star 0.15
		(0.13 – 0.42)	(-0.40 – +0.00)	(0.50 – 0.92)	(0.10 – 0.24)
		[0.01 – 1.15]	[-1.09 – +0.53]	[-0.56 – 0.98]	[0.03 – 0.57]
		{0.00 – 1.73}	{-1.73 – +1.36}	{-0.95 – 0.99}	{0.02 – 0.87}
GeoClaw	GTSM	0.55 \star 0.39	+0.02 \star -0.03	0.54 \star 0.63	0.15 \star 0.09
		(0.18 – 0.72)	(-0.40 – +0.38)	(0.37 – 0.79)	(0.04 – 0.19)
		[0.02 – 1.93]	[-1.49 – +1.64]	[-0.36 – 0.95]	[0.02 – 0.59]
		{0.00 – 4.24}	{-3.61 – +4.24}	{-0.81 – 1.00}	{0.01 – 1.41}

Supplementary Tbl. S7. Performance indicators for the evaluation of flood extents and high water marks (HWMs), when modeling inland floods with CaMa-Flood (totals/means and medians, separated by \star , with interquartile ranges in parentheses, Figs. 5 and 9).

	Indicator	GeoClaw	GeoClaw+CaMa-Flood	CaMa-Flood
Flood extents	MCC	+0.22 \star +0.10 (+0.04 – +0.21)	+0.23 \star +0.11 (+0.02 – +0.20)	+0.10 \star +0.00 (-0.01 – +0.11)
	F1	0.34 \star 0.15 (0.07 – 0.28)	0.37 \star 0.22 (0.11 – 0.34)	0.17 \star 0.04 (0.00 – 0.23)
	F2	0.20 \star 0.08 (0.04 – 0.16)	0.23 \star 0.12 (0.06 – 0.21)	0.09 \star 0.02 (0.00 – 0.13)
	TNR	89% \star 93% (87% – 98%)	85% \star 84% (73% – 91%)	95% \star 94% (81% – 100%)
	Bias	-0.22 \star -0.18 (-1.51 – +0.72)	+0.10 \star +0.55 (-0.27 – +1.37)	-1.00 \star -0.55 (-2.83 – +0.64)
HWMs	Hit rate	23.9%	41.6%	21.1%
	Error (m)	1.45 \star 1.13 (0.52 – 1.80)	1.61 \star 1.16 (0.55 – 2.20)	1.86 \star 1.29 (0.57 – 2.57)
	Bias (m)	-0.50 \star -0.47 (-1.38 – +0.56)	-0.34 \star -0.38 (-1.42 – +0.85)	-0.44 \star -0.37 (-1.65 – +0.88)

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